

Annotation scheme and guide

Background

This annotation scheme and guide were developed as part of ‘Digitaler Hass’, an interdisciplinary project of Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft (HTW) Berlin and Alice Salomon University (ASH) Berlin, that studies antisemitism, racism and conspiracy theories in online text corpora. The central goal of this document is to facilitate the annotation of online texts such as those published via messenger services or social media platforms with regard to occurrences of antisemitic and conspiracy theoretical statements. We have focused on narratives that are typical of pandemics such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The examples in the guide are mostly in German, as one of the goals of the project is to foster research based on large German-language corpora.

The scheme was adapted in the course of our own labeling of a Telegram dataset; the differences between the first and second versions are stated.

Details of the theoretical concepts, the annotation process, and the corpus we annotated will appear in a separate manuscript.

1 Annotation scheme

We consider the **two main labels** ‘antisemitism’ and ‘conspiracy theory’. If a text is deemed antisemitic or conspiracy-theoretical, (at least) one sub-label regarding **content** and **stance**, respectively, must be selected to differentiate the main label.

You are encouraged to select **only one content-related sub-label for antisemitism** which reflects the **dominating form** in the text. If the decision for one sub-label seems impossible, the selection of an additional label is possible. The **stance towards antisemitism** is expressed using a simple scheme differentiating mainly between an affirmative and critical attitude.

Conspiracy theory texts will be differentiated as to whether they name ‘actor’, ‘goal’, ‘strategy’, or ‘reference’. **All aspects identified in the respective text are to be selected.**

Stance towards articulated conspiracy-theoretical content is annotated based on the adapted version of the Rumor Interaction Analysis System developed by (Kou et al., 2017).

Background information on e.g. mentioned persons, organizations or platforms **should not be used for the decision**. For example, the reference to a video channel on which conspiracy theories are often communicated should not be used as a basis for deciding to label a text as conspiracy-theoretical. If there is any **uncertainty regarding the presence of**

antisemitism or conspiracy theory, do not set the label 'yes' and instead leave the text as unclassified.

We additionally offer two labels to indicate the context of the pandemic as well as references to the German Democratic Republic (GDR); the latter was included because, in addition to Nazi comparisons, references to the GDR were also frequently identified at demonstrations and in discourses of the 'Querdenker' scene.

The following table displays an overview of the categories considered during the annotation process. We provide the final version based on our insights from the first round of annotation, as well as the initial version of the annotation scheme.

Table 1: Annotation categories - final version

ID	Category	Description
MAIN CATEGORIES		
AS	antisemitism	Articulates antisemitism according to any explanation listed in the provided definitions and examples of the annotation guide.
CT	conspiracy theory	Articulates conspiracy theory content.
STANCE TOWARDS ANTISEMITIC CONTENT: only if main label = antisemitism		
AS-ST-AFF	affirmative	Takes an affirmative stance towards articulated antisemitism.
AS-ST-CRI	critical	Takes a critical stance towards articulated antisemitism.
AS-ST-NEU-UNC	neutral or unclear	Stance towards articulated antisemitism either neutral, as e.g. in news reports, or cannot be clearly categorized, e.g. due to missing context.
FORMS OF ANTISEMITISM: only if main label = antisemitism		
AS-PHA	post-Holocaust antisemitism	Argumentation strategies instrumentalizing the victims of the Holocaust for a political agenda; shifting the perpetrator-victim coordinates via relativizing Holocaust comparisons; e.g. comparisons or equations of the state measures against the pandemic with the persecution of Jews during the Holocaust.
AS-COD	encoded antisemitism	Encodings of antisemitic content and statements that do not necessarily mention Jews or the State of Israel; but may also turn generally against presumed or actual (economic or political) elites while deploying antisemitic codes or stereotypes such as actually or allegedly Jewish persons or

		dynasties, animal metaphors, disease and cancer metaphors, the 'lying press', codes referring to a financial Jewish elite.
AS-OTH	other forms of antisemitism	The content is considered antisemitic, but available sublabels are unsuitable or the annotator is uncertain which sublabel to apply or because none of the provided sublabels match.
STANCE TOWARDS CONSPIRACY THEORY CONTENT: only if main label = conspiracy theory		
CT-ST-BEL	belief	Expresses or strongly implies that the propagated theory is, or is very likely to be, true.
CT-ST-AUTH	authenticating	Refers explicitly to some authority, whether self or others, to support an argument or position.
CT-ST-DIR	directive	Encourages the audience to engage (or avoid engaging) in some course of action. This can be in support or in denial of conspiracy theory content.
CT-ST-RHE	rhetorical question	Asks a rhetorical or clearly leading question; may include "clickbait"-style headlines'.
CT-ST-DIS	disbelief	Expresses or strongly implies that a conspiracy theory is, or is very likely to be, false.
CT-ST-NEU	neutral or uncertain	Neutral towards conspiracy theory, e.g. in typical newspaper reporting, or stance cannot be categorized, e.g. due to missing or incomplete context.
TYPES OF CONSPIRACY THEORY CONTENT: only if main label = conspiracy theory		
CT-ACT	actor	One or more actors supposedly involved in a conspiracy are mentioned or implied, e.g. Bill Gates, Angela Merkel, 'the global elite', etc.
CT-STRAT	strategy	A strategy which serves to pursue a conspiracy is mentioned or implied, e.g. chip implantations via vaccinations.
CT-GOAL	goal	A goal which is supposed to be achieved through a conspiracy is mentioned or implied, e.g. world domination, Great Reset, etc.
CT-REF	reference	Reference to a known conspiracy theory is mentioned through hashtags (e.g. '#Deepstate') or single codes (e.g. 'Q').
OTHER REFERENCES		
COV	pandemic	Contains reference to the COVID-19 pandemic or the

	reference	Sars-Cov-2 virus. May be indirect, e.g. "virus".
GDR	GDR reference	Contains reference to the socialist regime of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR).
TECHNICAL		
TASK-M	memorize task	Marked for later reference, e.g. because it is considered as paradigmatic for a certain category.
TASK-U	task unsuitable	Generally unsuitable for the annotation process, contains sensitive information that is difficult to anonymize, is not German-language, too short and thus incomprehensible, or merely organizational content, e.g. calls for donations, live stream ads, etc.
TASK-REV	review required	Review by an additional annotator is required because the initial annotator is uncertain how to classify the task.

1.1 Differences to the initial version

Besides minor adjustment, we decided to remove the content sub-label 'structural antisemitism' from the scheme in the final version, mainly because annotators found it difficult to clearly distinguish the provided definition from messages interpreted as 'encoded'. We also removed the labels 'uncertain' and 'no' for the two main categories. In the final version of the annotation scheme, applying the labels 'antisemitism' or 'conspiracy theory' equates to the former choice 'antisemitism: yes', or 'conspiracy theory: yes'. Otherwise, the text should remain unlabeled and is then regarded as unclassified. In case of uncertainty about their labeling decision, annotators are asked to use the technical label 'review required'.

The initial version is listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Annotation categories - initial version

ID	Category	Description
ANTISEMITISM		
AS	antisemitism	Articulates antisemitism according to any explanation listed in Section 2.
NO-AS	no antisemitism	Does not articulate antisemitism.

UNCERT-AS	uncertain if antisemitism	Cannot certainly be categorized regarding antisemitism content.
STANCE TOWARDS ANTISEMITIC CONTENT: only if main label = Antisemitism		
AS-ST-AFF	affirmative	Takes an affirmative stance towards articulated antisemitism.
AS-ST-CRI	critical	Takes a critical stance towards articulated antisemitism.
AS-ST-NEU-UNC	neutral or unclear	Stance towards articulated antisemitism either neutral, as e.g. in news reports, or cannot be clearly categorized, e.g. due to missing context.
FORMS OF ANTISEMITISM: only if main label = Antisemitism		
AS-PHA	post-Holocaust antisemitism	Argumentation strategies instrumentalizing the victims of the Holocaust for a political agenda; shifting the perpetrator-victim coordinates via relativizing Holocaust comparisons; e.g. comparisons or equations of the state measures against the pandemic with the persecution of Jews during the Holocaust.
AS-COD	encoded antisemitism	Encodings of antisemitic content and statements that do not necessarily mention Jews or the State of Israel; but may also turn generally against presumed or actual (economic or political) elites while deploying antisemitic codes or stereotypes such as actually or allegedly Jewish persons or dynasties, animal metaphors, disease and cancer metaphors, the 'lying press', codes referring to a financial Jewish elite.
AS-STR	structurally antisemitic content	Simplified explanation attempts for societal or political phenomena, often involving simplified critiques of capitalism; attempts to identify graspable individuals or organizations who are then made responsible for the effects of the anonymous economic structures of capitalism; deploying the notion of a global elite (implicitly or explicitly presented as Jewish) controlling global economics (and politics).
AS-OTH	other forms of antisemitism	The content is considered antisemitic, but available sublabels are unsuitable or the annotator is uncertain which sublabel to apply.
CONSPIRACY THEORY		
CT	conspiracy theory	Articulates conspiracy theory content.

NO-CT	no conspiracy theory	Does not articulate conspiracy theory content.
UNCERT-CT	uncertain if conspiracy theory	Cannot certainly be categorized regarding conspiracy theory content.
STANCE TOWARDS CONSPIRACY THEORY CONTENT: only if main label = Conspiracy theory		
CT-ST-BEL	belief	Expresses or strongly implies that the propagated theory is, or is very likely to be, true.
CT-ST-AUTH	authenticating	Refers explicitly to some authority, whether self or others, to support an argument or position.
CT-ST-DIR	directive	Encourages the audience to engage (or avoid engaging) in some course of action. This can be in support or in denial of conspiracy theory content.
CT-ST-RHE	rhetorical question	Asks a rhetorical or clearly leading question; may include “clickbait”-style headlines’.
CT-ST-DIS	disbelief	Expresses or strongly implies that a conspiracy theory is, or is very likely to be, false.
CT-ST-NEU	neutral or uncertain	Neutral towards conspiracy theory, e.g. in typical newspaper reporting, or stance cannot be categorized, e.g. due to missing or incomplete context.
TYPES OF CONSPIRACY THEORY CONTENT: only if main label = Conspiracy theory		
CT-ACT	actor	One or more actors supposedly involved in a conspiracy are mentioned or implied, e.g. Bill Gates, Angela Merkel, ‘the global elite’, etc.
CT-STRAT	strategy	A strategy which serves to pursue a conspiracy is mentioned or implied, e.g. chip implantations via vaccinations.
CT-GOAL	goal	A goal which is supposed to be achieved through a conspiracy is mentioned or implied, e.g. world domination, Great Reset, etc.
CT-REF	reference	Reference to a known conspiracy theory is mentioned through hashtags (e.g. ‘#Deepstate’) or single codes (e.g. ‘Q’).
OTHER REFERENCES		

COV	pandemic reference	Contains reference to the COVID-19 pandemic or the Sars-Cov-2 virus. May be indirect, e.g. "virus".
GDR	GDR reference	Contains reference to the socialist regime of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR).
TECHNICAL		
TASK-M	memorize task	Marked for later reference, e.g. because it is considered as paradigmatic for a certain category.
TASK-U	task unsuitable	Generally unsuitable for the annotation process, e.g. because its content is unrelated, not comprehensible, or because it contains sensitive information that is difficult to anonymize. Not German-language Too short and thus incomprehensible Merely organizational content, e.g. calls for donations, live stream ads, ...

1.2 Examples for annotation

The table includes examples for the different categories. The examples are sorted according to the category groups (e.g. antisemitism: main label) and the category that it should highlight is set in **bold letters**. Each example is prepared in a table consisting of the text (first row), all labels related to antisemitism and conspiracy theory (second row), and justifications (last row) for **selected** categories.

Note that the examples were created according to the initial scheme.

Antisemitism: main label

<i>Ibuprofen hat völlig ausgereicht, da braucht man nicht mRNA Versuchskaninchen zu spielen (Twitter)</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		strategy	belief
		suggests that mRNA vaccines are used to experiment on people	

<i>Und da ganz oben werden die Geschichten und Bilder über den Nahostkonflikt einprogrammiert und verbreitet. Ob Syrien, Irak, Palästina, oder Corona. Die Welt ist eine Bühne der Freimaurer und Zionisten</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
antisemitism	affirmative	actors	belief

encoded		strategy strategy	
antisemitism: suggests that 'Nahostkonflikt' is orchestrated by 'Freimaurer' and 'Zionisten' encoded: reference to Zionisten and Freimaurer		actors: 'da ganz oben', 'Freimaurer und Zionisten' strategy: different wars and conflicts ('Syrien, Irak, Palästina') and the pandemic	

"Oktober 2021: Der Spiegel erhält von der Bill-und-Melinda-Gates-Stiftung 2,9 Mio. Dollar. November 2021: Der Spiegel propagiert die Impfpflicht für alle. Nicht wertend gemeint, nur eine chronologische Auflistung von Fakten... #impfpflichtjetzt #VierteWelle #Impfgegner #Corona" (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		actors strategy	belief
		actors: Bill-und-Melinda-Gates Stiftung strategy: the newspaper 'Der Spiegel' allegedly propagates the compulsory vaccination	The author believes in the conspiracy theory that the Gates Foundation is colluding with the press to manipulate people into getting vaccinated

Antisemitism: content-related sub-labels

Eine amerikanische Investment-Bankerin erklärt Dir genau, was hinter Corona und der künstlich geschaffenen Krise der Gesundheitssysteme steckt. Wenn Du dieses Video gesehen hast, verstehst Du, was gerade auf der ganzen Welt passiert!

Es geht nur an der Oberfläche um Gesundheitsschutz oder um Bekämpfung eines Virus. Im Hintergrund wird etwas anderes beabsichtigt...

Catherine Austin Fitts:

"Covid 19 ist wie ein Staatsstreich - dahinter steckt Katastrophen-Kapitalismus, der die Milliardäre immer reicher macht..."

"Covid 19 ist die Institution der Kontrolle, die notwendig ist, um den Planeten von einem demokratischen Prozess in eine Technokratie zu verwandeln. Was wir beobachten ist eine Veränderung der Kontrolle und eine Konstruktion neuer Kontrollsysteme..."

Der Hammer, ab Min. 13:13 erklärt sie den Transhumanismus:

"Die von Gates geplante Impfung ist wie eine Hintertür, die geschaffen wird, um Zugang zum System des Geimpften zu haben..."

"Im Grunde geht es darum, dass man die Menschen (mit ihren finanziellen Transaktionen) digital identifizieren und verfolgen kann. Eine Totalüberwachung mit geplanten Kryptowährungen - damit wird auch das Sozialverhalten des Menschen gesteuert..." (Wie es bereits in China geschieht. Das gefällt natürlich machaffinen Politikern)..."

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
structural	affirmative	actors	belief

		strategy goal	authenticating
Economic mechanisms are communicated in an abridged form, explained by an investment banker who is assumed to be familiar with the system. Reference to disaster capitalism.			

"Der Orden (der Jesuiten) kontrolliert daher wohl seit der Französischen Revolution und den Napoleonischen Kriegen das berühmte Haus Rothschild, nach welchem Jesuiten-geführten Kreuzzug die Familie Rothschild die „Wächter der Vatikan-Finzen (1830)“ wurden." (Eric Jon Phelps)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded	affirmative	actors strategy goal	neutral or uncertain
the Rothschild family used as a code for Jewish domination		Jesuits (actors) are controlling historical developments since the French Revolution and the Rothshild family conspire with the Jesuits to control history and the Vatikan finance (goal), and in that way the world, using the 'Kreuzzug' (strategy)	known conspiracy myth set in quotation marks. Without context, the author's position is not clear.

Ich glaube "Ich spreche seit über einem Jahr die "Clique" hinter den Impfungen und der sog. Neuen Weltordnung an!

Was ist das Resultat?

- 1. 5000 Händler listen meine Bio-Produkte aus*
 - 2. Partner distanzieren sich*
 - 3. Abfüller füllen nicht mehr ab!*
 - 4. Banken kündigen*
 - 5. Presse hetzt auf allen Kanälen*
 - 6. Antifa terrorisiert*
 - 7. ""Staatsschutz"" der BRD-Firma von Rothschild ""ermittelt""*
 - 8. BRD-Haftbefehl erlassen*
 - 9. Reicht scheinbar nicht, also nochmal Europol nachschieben*
 - 10. Werde von käuflichem Verräter ... ""verraten""*
 - 11. Kann nicht mehr nach Deutschland!*
 - 12. Wirtschaftlich bis auf Reste zerschlagen!*
 - 13. Besteller-Kochbücher werden nicht nachgedruckt*
- [.....] (Telegram)*

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded	affirmative	actors strategy goal	belief

2.4 Reference to antisemitic New World Order conspiracy theory and reference to Rothschild in connection with power and conspiracies		actors: die 'Clique', 'those behind it' goal: new world order (Neue Weltordnung) strategy: vaccinations additional details provided in the listing, e.g. 'Staatsschutz' being bought by Rothschild	
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Unser Land wurde durch Linksextremisten, Stasi Widerlinge, SED Mauermörder, Zionisten, Freimaurer, Bilderberger, Sozialisten, bezahlte Söldner/Terroristen, korrupte Politverbrecher und Pädophile in hohen Positionen und Ämtern verseucht! Gefährlicher ist KEIN Virus!

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded structural	affirmative	actors	belief
encoded: reference to "Zionisten, Freimaurer, Bilderberger". structural: reference to "Bilderberger"			

Es gibt ca. 100.000 Juden in Deutschland. Wenn wir die gleichen Verhältnisse wie für den Durchschnitt annehmen, sind davon dann ca. 10.000 Erw. ungeimpft. Daher wurden auch gestern wieder 10.000 Juden in Deutschland durch 2G vom öffentlichen Leben ausgegrenzt. #NieWieder (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
post-Holocaust	affirmative	no conspiracy theory	
The 2G regulations and their impact on the Jewish population are brought together by the hashtag #NieWieder with the demand that the Holocaust never be repeated.			

Heute soll das Ermächtigungsgesetz beschlossen werden. Welche Macht das hat, ist vielen nicht bewusst. Zur Erinnerung: Die, die Anne Frank vor den Nazis versteckten, handelten gegen das Gesetz. Die Leute, die sie umbrachten nicht. (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
post-Holocaust	affirmative	no conspiracy theory	

Wenn es eine #Corona Pandemie gibt, #Zionisten aber nicht aufhören können, einheimische #Palästinenser zu unterdrücken. #FreePalestine URL

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
other forms	affirmative	no conspiracy theory	
concerns Israel			

Antisemitism: stance-related sub-labels

<i>#Israel is now attacking ppl with diseases, immunocompromised, all in the name of corona! THIS IS EXACTLY what the nazis did at the early stages. #Israhell! #NeverAgain ? Liars. Evil. #Fascists (Twitter)</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
other	affirmative	actors strategy	belief
antisemitism: Manifestations of antisemitism related to Israel (2.2.14) other: 2.2.14 is the main narrative, PHA not central	Israel called liars and fascists.	suggests that Israel (actors) has a hidden agenda ('Liars') and utilizes Corona ('all in the name of corona') as a pretext to harm sick people (strategy). Goal is missing.	

<i>Mein Nachbar, der glaubt, die Juden wären an der Pandemie schuld.</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
other forms	unclear	no conspiracy theory	
	mentions antisemitic narrative, but author's stance towards it is unclear		

<i>Nur haben sie damals gesagt, die Juden sind an der Pandemie schuld, und nicht, die pandemie gibt's nicht, sie ist nur von Juden erfunden (Twitter)</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
other forms	critical	no conspiracy theory	
	Mentions antisemitic narrative, but author provides arguments to deconstruct it		

Conspiracy theory: main label

305,aerzte,1351139793,25308,2021-10-25 10:30:28+00:00,"SPECIAL 🇺🇸 Dr. Ryan Cole 🇺🇸 + Untertitel 🇩🇪

KREBS EXPLODIERT BEI ""GEIMPFTEN"" 🌟🧬
 CANCER EXPLODES IN ""VACCINATED""

""...dann listete er die Anzahl der Krebserkrankungen auf, die er in einem Zeitraum von sechs Wochen gesehen hat, die er in seiner 40-jährigen Karriere noch NIE gesehen hat...

UNERKLÄRLICHE Krebsarten, die wirklich ungewöhnlich altern, die wirklich DICK sind und wirklich AGGRESSIVER Krebs ist im Vergleich zu dem, was wir aus dem Labor her kennen..."

📍 Dr. Ryan Cole aus Idaho/USA, ist ein zertifizierter Pathologe und Inhaber & Betreiber eines Diagnostiklabors. Er berichtet, dass er bei ""geimpften"" Patienten einen massiven Anstieg verschiedener Autoimmunerkrankungen und Krebserkrankungen feststellt.

📍 Dr. Ryan Cole - 20-FACHER ANSTIEG VON KREBS

📍 STIFTUNG-CORONA-AUSSCHUSS 🧠 ▶ LISTE
 ALLE Anhörungen als einzelne Videos.
 📍 t.me/CoronaAusschussAlleAnhoerungen (Telegram)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		no conspiracy theory	
		this is rather disinformation since neither actors nor a goal or a strategy can be recognized, and there is no explicit reference to an existing conspiracy theory. Reference to CoronaAusschuss is not sufficient to label it as a conspiracy theory.	

@USER Der Herr Innenminister #Seehofer sollte sich mal endlich um die Verbreiter kümmern, die sog Querdenker schüren Unsicherheit, Unruhe und Hass, bedrohen Impfzentren, Schüler- Wissenschaftler:innen, Presse u Menschen, die sich an die Regeln halten (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		no conspiracy theory	

So lange die Medien ihr Brennglas rein auf die reisserischen Randgruppen halten, da diese sich besser verkaufen lassen und noch systemuntreuer erscheinen als die wirklich kritischen Gruppen wie die Querdenker, die sich von Radikalen distanzieren, braucht man einen langen Atem.

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		uncertain if conspiracy theory	

		the narrative of the lying, manipulated press is served but this is only a hint of a conspiracy theory	
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Nebenwirkungen bei den Corona-Gen Injektionen? Kein Problem, einfach löschen. Die vielen Toten stören beim Great Reset. (Telegram)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		conspiracy theory strategy reference goal	belief rhetorical question
		reference to the known conspiracy theory of the "Great Reset", vaccine as a strategy, and the great reset as a goal.	

Conspiracy theory: content sub-label

Jetzt kommt der Great Reset! Noch ist die Pandemie nicht zu Ende. Aber trotzdem wissen wir schon, wer davon profitiert. Es ist die globale Elite und diese Leute haben einen perfiden Plan URL

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded	affirmative	actors goal strategy reference	belief
refers to the 'global elite' behind the Great Reset.		The 'global elite' (actors) has a perfidious plan which involves the pandemic (strategy) for the Great Reset (goal, reference)	

@USER Diese Umfrageplattformen dienen nur dazu, Emotionen aufzugreifen und ihnen eine vermeintliche Wirkung zu geben, die dann verraucht wird. Ich glaube Change org wird von Soros finanziert, keiner dieser Emotionsfänger hat zu irgendwas geführt.

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded	affirmative	actors strategy	belief

Reference to Soros indicates 'Jewish string pullers'		Set piece of a conspiracy theory which says that opinions are manipulated through change.org (strategy) which is financed by Soros (actors)	
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<i>Wie sagte "Q" so schön? "Enjoy the show" (Telegram)</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		reference	belief
		code 'Q' referring to QAnon conspiracy theory listed but no other aspect (actors, strategy, goal).	

<i>#Corona #impfpflicht #impfzwang Weltgesundheitsstreffen in Berlin 2018, mit dabei Merkel, Bill Gates, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus (WHO) und auch bereits Uğur Şahin, der uns 2020/21 mit Biontech-Pfizer den Zaubertrank bringen wird. Alles reiner Zufall, hat mit Nichts zu tun (Twitter)</i>			
antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		actors strategy	belief
		various individuals, in part representing certain organizations such as WHO (actors) use the vaccine (strategy) without elaborating a goal.	'#impfzwang' suggests the author believes in the theory

Conspiracy theory: stance sub-label

<p>✗ Bitte seid vorsichtig Leute! ✗</p> <p><i>Der Antifa-Schmutz versucht euch zu schaden und eure Jobs, Psyche, Familien und im allgemeinen euer Leben zu zerstören wie sie es bei Attila und vielen anderen Menschen auch versuchen und bei einigen teilweise schaffen. Sie stellen Fragen im Chat, die sich eigentlich jeder Freigeist selbst beantworten kann. Reagiert man auf solche Fragen und die Antwort stimmt nicht mit Lügipedia überein, wird man privat angeschrieben und in die 130er-Falle manövriert.</i></p> <p><i>Dieses linke Drecksack!</i></p> <p><i>Sie versuchen hier generell auf die unterschiedlichsten Arten und Weisen unserer Bewegung zu schaden. Bitte lasst euch nicht verarschen und vergesst nie:</i></p> <p><i>Sie geben sich als alles mögliche aus um ihre Propaganda zu betreiben. Sie unterwandern, lügen, fälschen, tragen falsche Flaggen und haben weder Ehre, Anstand noch Respekt. Sie schämen sich nicht, wenn sie eine Maske spielen und wie gedruckt lügen. Im Gegenteil. Sie erfreuen sich an der teils authentischen Wirkung ihrer Lügen und jedem, der auf sie hereinfällt.</i></p> <p><i>Sie sind - genau wie der Feind selbst, dessen Schergen sie sind - durch und durch link und verlogen. Falsche Ratten!</i></p>
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Hebt euer Bewusstsein an um die abstrusen Manipulationsstrategien des Feindes zu erkennen.
 Bleibt wachsam, Brüder und Schwestern!
 Die Menschlichkeit, die Liebe und das Gute werden siegen, wenn wir als Menschheitsfamilie zusammen
 kommen und gemeinsam für diese eintreten
 Für das geplante "Sklaverei-System" gibt es 5 Säulen, die die Grundlage darstellen...

1. Tech-Leute, die die Clouds für die Datenmengen bauen (Telekommunikation, 5-G, 6-G...)
2. Das Militär, welches sich mit dem Weltraum beschäftigt (Satelliten)...
3. Big Pharma, die die Impfungen mit geheimnisvollen, dna-modifizierenden Stoffen produzieren...
4. Medien, die die Propaganda verbreiten...
5. Zentralbanken, die die Kryptosysteme (neue Form der Zahlungsmitteln) entwickeln...

Man verhindert, wo es nur geht, dass der Bürger in seinem Alltag erkennt, dass die Akteure dieser Säulen
 gemeinsam an der Etablierung des geplanten Systems arbeiten...

Augenöffnend war auch die Schilderung der Expertin, was der wahre Hintergrund der Black Lives
 Matter-Unruhen in Amerika sind! Es geht um Immobilienspekulationen der Milliardäre...

Lösung:
 Transparenz verdirbt das Spiel der Manipulatoren! Deshalb empfehle ich Dir, dieses Video anzusehen. Wir
 Bürger haben die Macht, die Akteure zu stoppen!
 Wie, das erklärt die Expertin am Ende des Videos. Super wichtig!!!
 URL (Telegram)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
encoded	affirmative	actor goal strategy reference	belief directive authenticating
		the actors are implied as 'der Feind selbst, dessen Schergen sie sind', and they plan a 'slavery system (goal) using different strategies as 5G etc. Various conspiracy theories such as Big Pharma or 5G are referenced.	

@USER Ich vertraue doch keiner Okkupationsverwaltung, die eine gefakte Pandemie benutzt und ein ganzes
 Volk bewusst foltert und nun auch noch genmanipulieren will, ich kenne die ganzen Handlungspapiere und
 Events (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		actors strategy goal	belief
		'Okkupationsverwaltung' as actor that uses the 'fake pandemic' as a strategy to torture and genetically manipulate the entire population (goal)	Strongly implies the theory is true ('ich vertraue doch keiner Okkupationsverwaltung', 'ich kenne die ganzen Handlungspapier und Events')

⚠ WARNUNG ⚠

Angela Merkel beschleunigt die Flutung der BRD mit Muslimen, um einem von ihr gefürchteten Erwachen des deutschen Volkes zuvor zu kommen.
 Daher trommelt nun der Staatsfunk verstärkt alle linksradikalen Überfremdungsfanatiker zusammen, um eine erwartete Gegenwehr des deutschen Volkes zu verhindern.
 Das erste Ziel ist die Überflutung unseres Abendlandes mit muslimischen Invasoren, um das deutsche Volk zu Vernichten.
 Das ist Völkermord und muss umgehend gestoppt werden.
 Ich empfehle als ersten Schritt jeden einzelnen eindringlich, die Zahlung von GEZ unverzüglich einzustellen.
 URL (Telegram)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		explicit	directive
			E.g. the last sentence formulates a recommendation and request to the readers.

Ungeimpft, erzählt die Verschwörung über die Neue Weltordnung, hält Corona für Ungefährlich, alles Quatsch und verarsche was die Regierung erzählt und nun auf der Intensivstation wegen Corona.
 Lasst euch Impfen und glaubt den shit nicht, der erzählt wird. (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		fragmented	disbelief directive
			Describes the message of the film 'Unvaccinated' as nonsense ('alles Quatsch')

"Plötzlicher Tod russischer Regierungs- und Corona-Kritiker nur Zufall? ✓ URL (Telegram)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		strategy	rhetorical question
		Claim that critics of the Russian government and Corona are being killed and that there is a plan behind it.	Fragments of a conspiracy theory packaged as a rhetorical question.

"Es war kein Corona, kein Virus, aber viel Technologie und Verschwörung."
 Manifeste conspirationniste // Ein Manifest der Verschwörung (Twitter)

antisemitism (content/stance)		conspiracy theory (content/stance)	
no antisemitism		fragmented	neutral or unclear
			stance cannot be categorized, e.g. due to missing or incomplete context.

Further examples

GDR Reference: "@USER Ja genau. Das ist die gleiche Lüge, wie : ""Mit dem Wissen von heute werden wir keine Geschäfte mehr schließen"". Oder: ""Niemand hat die Absicht eine Mauer zu errichten."" Oder: ""Es wird keine Impfpflicht geben--auch nicht durch die Hintertür.""(Twitter)
Task unsuitable: "@USER All done, boss! Your download link: URL Psst...your new downloads will always be there, even when I don't reply. See URL if you've got any questions.👍

2 Annotation guide for antisemitic content

2.1 Basic definition

Antisemitism is a certain perception of Jews, which may be expressed as hatred toward Jews. Antisemitism can be directed toward Jewish or non-Jewish individuals and/or their property, toward Jewish community institutions and religious facilities.

2.2 Concretizations

Concrete antisemitic expressions according to the IHRA definition which are particularly relevant for our focus are:

2.2.1 Calls for the killing or harming of Jews in the name of a radical ideology or extremist religious belief, as well as aiding, abetting, or justifying such acts.

2.2.2 False, dehumanizing, demonizing, or stereotyping accusations against Jews or the power of Jews as a collective - including myths about a Jewish world conspiracy or about Jewish control of the media, business, government, or other social institutions.

2.2.3 Holding Jews as a people responsible for actual or imputed wrongdoing by individual Jews, individual Jewish groups, or even non-Jews.

2.2.4 Using symbols and images associated with traditional antisemitism (e.g., the Christ-killing accusation or the ritual murder legend) to describe Israel or Israelis.

Furthermore, the following tropes and stereotypes concretize our working definition (full list available in (Jikeli et al., 2019)):

2.2.5 A Supposed “Jewish character” (e.g. greedy; immensely rich; exploitative)

2.2.6 Supposed “Jewish physical stereotypes” (e.g. hooked noses; pointed beards)

2.2.7 Antisemitic imagery (e.g. lavishly rich capitalists; hooked-nosed communists; parasites)

2.2.8 Supposed “Jewish crimes” (e.g. the charge of deicide/ killing Jesus; working with alleged conspiratorial groups thriving for world power, such as Rothschilds, Freemasons, Illuminati, Jewish lobby, Zionist Lobby, Zionist Neocons; using blood from non-Jews for ritual purposes)

2.2.9 The demonization of things associated with Jews or of individuals seen as representative of Jews (e.g. the demonization of synagogues; demonization of prominent Jews, such as George Soros)

2.2.10 Nonvisual memes or recurrent phraseology that are part of an antisemitic repertoire in different historical and cultural contexts; e.g. “Jews are the children/ spawn of Satan; synagogue of Satan”; (...) all pro-Jewish or pro-Israeli organizations are funded/ operated by the Mossad)

2.2.11 Calls for punishment or justification of Jewish suffering, mostly in religious contexts

2.2.12 Holocaust denial and distortion, as described in the IHRA Definition of Antisemitism and the more detailed IHRA Working Definition of Holocaust Denial and Distortion: “Holocaust denial is discourse and propaganda that deny the historical reality and the extent of the extermination of the Jews by the Nazis and their accomplices during World War II [...]”

2.2.13 Endorsing Nazism, i.e. endorsing the systematic killings of Jews by the Nazis (and their helpers); often by the affirmative use of pro-Nazi memes and symbols.

2.2.14 Manifestations of antisemitism related to Israel, especially comparisons of contemporary Israeli policy to that of the Nazis

2.2.15 Symbols that have an antisemitic connotation, i.e. positive references to Nazism or to the Holocaust, such as the swastika or other Nazi or Nazi-predecessor flags

2.3 Post-Holocaust antisemitism (PHA)

Manifestations of post-Holocaust antisemitism explicitly name Jews as part of argumentation strategies which instrumentalize the victims of the Holocaust for a political agenda and at the

same time shift the perpetrator-victim coordinates by undertaking relativizing Holocaust comparisons.

With regard to the past, PHA historically relativizes the Shoah and infamously instrumentalizes the antisemitic policy of extermination. With regard to the present, it allows conspiracy theorists to demonize and delegitimize democratically legitimized rulings and measures by describing themselves as victims of a dictatorial state.

In times of the COVID-19 pandemic, we encounter forms of post-Holocaust antisemitism in comparisons or equations of the state measures to combat the pandemic with the National Socialist persecution of Jews.

Examples

Giftspritze, Chip

Vaccinations against COVID-19 are called “Giftspritze” (engl. “poison injection”) by some. Allegedly, it is claimed, vaccination serves to decimate humanity. Other conspiracy narratives about vaccination claim that it is used to implant a chip or that Bill Gates is trying to enrich himself. That ‘the Jews’ are often suspected to be behind vaccination programs is no accident. Antisemitic narratives about vaccination have a long tradition in Germany, dating back to the beginning of vaccination in the 19th century. As early as in the NS propaganda newspaper ‘Der Stürmer’ there are caricatures that are supposed to prove a connection between vaccinations and ‘the Jews’.

‘Ungeimpft’-Stern

Some conspiracy ideologues have worn a yellow star with the inscription ‘Ungeimpft’ (‘Unvaccinated’) at demonstrations against the Corona protections. The message emanating from these anti-vaccine ideologues is, ‘Wir sind die neuen Juden’ (‘We are the new Jews’) which is a classic perpetrator-victim reversal. Other narratives go as far as to equate virologist Christian Drosten with SS doctor Josef Mengele.

Sophie Scholl

Sophie Scholl was an anti-Nazi political activist and member of the resistance group ‘Weiße Rose’, who was executed together with her brother in 1943. Within the Querdenken movement, comparisons with the historical figure are made, especially at demonstrations. For example, at a Querdenken demonstration in Hannover, a 22-year-old woman who became ‘famous’ as ‘Jana from Kassel’ got up on stage and said that she felt like Sophie Scholl because she was in the resistance against the COVID-19 restrictions.

2.4 Encoded antisemitism

Linguistic encodings of antisemitic content and statements that do not mention Jews or the State of Israel, e.g. narratives which do not explicitly or not necessarily mentions Jews as initiators of the pandemic and the resulting global crisis, but instead turn generally against presumed or actual (economic or political) elites while deploying antisemitic codes or stereotypes. Note that the occurrence of phrases, words or names such as 'Bill Gates' alone is typically not sufficient to label a text antisemitic.

Antisemitic codes can be articulated consciously or unconsciously. The following examples describe some common stereotypes which are by no means exhaustive:

Examples

Actually or allegedly Jewish persons or dynasties: e.g. Rothschild, Rockefeller, George Soros, Mark Zuckerberg, Bill Gates, Angela Merkel

Animal metaphors: e.g. octopus, snake, pig, rat

Disease and cancer metaphors: Virus, germ, parasite, cancer, tumor

Codes referring to the 'lying press' trope: "Lügenpresse", "Pinocchio-Press", "Lückenpresse", "Systemmedien"

Codes referring to a financial (Jewish) elite in control of global events:

Financial elite, high finance, East coast, Wall street, rapacious financial capital, also see Section 2.5.

2.5 Structurally antisemitic discourses

Simplified explanation attempts for societal or political phenomena, often involving simplified critiques of capitalism, that are structurally similar to modern antisemitism, specifically attempts to identify graspable individuals or organizations who are then made responsible for the effects of the anonymous economic structures of capitalism.

While the concrete sphere of capitalism, represented by supposedly 'honest' and 'useful' labor, the production of basic goods, and industrial capital, is being glorified, the abstract sphere of the capitalist society, represented by money, the stock market, 'artificial' profit, and financial capital, is being demonized and identified with 'the Jews' who are imagined as those who profit from capitalism as well as from capitalist crises.

Core features of these discourses are (a) a personalization and (b) a moralization of critiques of capitalism.

Examples

Structurally antisemitic discourses aim at holding concrete individuals (or groups) responsible for the capitalist system, which is at the same time presented as anonymous and impalpable. This is for example the case in discourses about a **'global financial elite'**, **'high finance'**, references to **'East coast'** or **'Wall Street'**, or **juxtapositions of 'rapacious' versus 'productive' capital**. These narratives deploy the notion of a **global elite** (implicitly or explicitly presented as Jewish) **controlling global politics and economics**.

3 Annotation guide for conspiracy theories

3.1 Basic definition

Conspiracy theories formulate the strong belief that a secret group of people, who have the evil goal of taking over an institution, a country and even the entire world, intentionally cause complex, and in most cases unsolved, events and phenomena.

A conspiracy theory can thus be considered an effort to explain some event or practice by reference to the machinations of powerful people, who have also managed to conceal their role.

Such a narrative is based on a simple dualism between good vs. evil, which leaves no space for mistakes as well as unintentional, unforeseeable effects of more complex dynamics. Our definition also implies that the involved individuals or groups pursue malignant intentions and that the events or practices a given conspiracy theory refers to is of a significant relevance for the public. All these theories and narratives have some commonalities: On the one hand, they fantasize a homogeneous entity of the "powerful" or the "elite" who have or want to gain control over the rest of the world, and who use and exploit the pandemic for the sake of their own benefit. On the other hand, they reproduce an us/them logic.

A conspiracy theory needs **actors** (e.g. corrupt elites) who supposedly pursue a concrete malicious **goal** (control of the population) using a **strategy** (e.g. the insertion of a microchip via vaccinations). In this respect, a conspiracy theory differs from disinformation which refers to the intentional circulation of incorrect and misleading information, or misinformation which unintentionally disseminates incorrect information, while a conspiracy theory creates an alternative interpretation of events.

We annotate which of the components (actors, goal, strategy) appear in a given text. In addition, we label if a **reference to a known conspiracy theory** is provided as hashtags (e.g. '#QAnon', '#deepstate') or codes (e.g. 'Q').

3.2 Concretizations

We could assert that conspiracy theories **directly connected to the COVID-19 pandemic** argue on **three levels**, each of which relates differently to the origin and even the existence of SARS-CoV-2:

3.2.1 Questioning the existence of the virus, and thus the pandemic in general, for example, suspecting the pandemic was invented by governments to restrict our fundamental civil rights.

3.2.2 It is argued that **the virus is deliberately produced in a laboratory** to be used, among other things, as a bioweapon, or to cause forced vaccinations from which pharmaceutical companies profit, etc.

3.2.3 Downplaying the pandemic: the disease is apparently a harmless flu, the consequences and scope of which are communicated in a highly exaggerated way by mainstream media, governments and international organizations with the intention of, yet again, forced vaccination, **control and restriction of the freedom** of common citizens.

Besides conspiracy theories directly connected to the pandemic, **older conspiracy theories are disseminated and linked to the pandemic**. We might distinguish two main conspiracy theories:

3.2.4 The state/government is demonized (**statephobia**). There is a great array of different conspiracy theories suspecting that the state /government or supranational bodies like WHO, UNO, etc. are trying to gain control over their citizens (or the world) and destroy democratic structures.

3.2.5 Mistrust towards technological developments. **Anti-modern** conspiracy theories describe certain technological development as part of a big plan by a certain group to control the world.

3.2.6 Conspiracy theories related to (supposedly) **secret societies** (e.g. freemason, jesuits, illuminati).

3.2.7 Racist and suprematist fantasies and narratives

Examples

COVID-10 lab-leak

The claim that SARS-CoV-2 originated in a laboratory in China, namely in the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) and spread from there through a leak. This leak is for most advocates of this narrative accidental and through negligence, some claim that the virus was intentionally released. (cf. **3.2.2**)

Bioweapon

Claims that COVID-19 was "manufactured" in a bioweapons laboratory in order to be used as a bioweapon. A superpower (varies, for example, China, USA, Israel) pursues the goal of using the virus to exterminate and decimate the world population and to seize world domination. In a next step, the surviving population is to be brought into line through forced vaccinations. (cf. **3.2.2**)

Puppet master (Marionettenspieler, Strippenzieher)

Idea of a secret "puppet master" or "string puller." For a long time, the image has been spread that "the Jew" secretly pulls the strings in the background and thus directs world events. The narrative bonds with the 'Dolchstößlegende' (stabbing legend). (cf. **3.2.4**)

Bill Gates

Belief that "greedy" businessmen around Microsoft founder Bill Gates are responsible for the pandemic by bringing the virus into being so that subsequent vaccinations could insert a microchip into human bodies and gain "total domination" over people. Bill Gates is assumed to control governments and large international organizations like the WHO, allowing him to implement his long prepared plan to depopulate the world. (cf. **3.2.2, 3.2.4**)

Anti-Vaxx

Claims that COVID-19 vaccinations are poisonous, or instruments for implementing mind control over the world population by implanting microchips into the bodies of vaccinated people (also cf. 'Bill Gates' conspiracy theory). It also appears in the form of propaganda against the introduction of compulsory vaccination. (cf. **3.2.2, 3.2.4**)

QAnon

Towards the end of 2017, a new conspiracy myth was spread for the first time. At its center is the myth that a satanic child trafficking circle, behind which a network known as the cabal, is using the blood of children to extract a substance that supposedly prevents aging

processes. The idea that a conspiracy of international and powerful elites was torturing children for its own purposes updated a multitude of anti-Judaic and antisemitic stereotypes, be it ritual murder legends, the idea of a Jewish state within the state, or a global Jewish world conspiracy. From the beginning, however, Jews were also explicitly named as actors in the alleged conspiracy (cf. **3.2.4**)

5G

Claims that COVID-19 is spread via 5G mobile networks, or that electromagnetic fields caused by 5G cellphone masts or the higher frequency of the 5G technology damage the immune system and thus increase the risk of a COVID-19 infection. (cf. **3.2.5**)

Big Pharma

A group of conspiracy theories claiming that the medical community in general and pharmaceutical companies in particular, especially large corporations, operate for sinister purposes and against the public good, and that they conceal effective treatments, or even cause and worsen a wide range of diseases for the only purpose of profitability. Specific variations of the conspiracy theory have included the following claims: natural alternative remedies to health problems are being suppressed; drugs for the treatment of HIV/AIDS are ineffective and harmful; a cure for all cancers has been discovered but hidden from the public; COVID-19 vaccines are ineffective and alternative cures are available. A range of authors have shown these claims to be false, though some nevertheless maintain that other criticisms of the pharmaceutical industry are legitimate. (cf. **3.2.5**)

New World Order (NWO), The Great Reset

NWO propagates the idea that a global elite aims at establishing a totalitarian supranational world government in order to e.g. abolish people's liberties. In the COVID-19 pandemic, the myth of the "Great Reset" has been added, suggesting that some world leaders have planned the pandemic to take over control over the world economy. (cf. **3.2.6**)

Child Murderer (Kindermörder)

The ritual murder legend from the Middle Ages states that Jews would use the blood of (Christian) children for baking. This legend was handed down over centuries and can be found today in updated forms – e.g. as part of the QAnon conspiracy theory (cf. **3.2.6**)

The Great Replacement (Der Große Austausch)

This myth claims that a global elite secretly plans to destroy the Christian-white population by replacing them through non-white and/or Muslim people using massive immigration. The

global elite is believed to be Jewish, often mentioning the US-American George Soros. The myth ties in with the antisemitic notion of a “Jewish world conspiracy”. (cf. **3.2.7**)

References to known conspiracy theories

The following terms serve as examples of frequently used as references to popular conspiracy theories in the context of COVID-19:

QAnon, WWG1WGA, Q, followthewhiterabbit, trusttheplan, savethechildren, saveourchildren, Deepstate, Plandemie, Pizzagate, Pedogate, NWO

References

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